

IMPROVING LISTENING SKILLS USING ANIMATION FOR PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract. *In this article will be discussed improving listening skills through an animation-based approach.*

Keywords: *audio and video materials, communicative competence, auditory and pronunciation skills, rhythmic and intonation skills, foreign language.*

Аннотация. *В этой статье мы обсудим улучшение навыков аудирования с помощью подхода, основанного на анимации.*

Ключевые слова: *аудио- и видеоматериалы, коммуникативная компетенция, слухо-произносительный навык, ритмико-интонационный навык, иностранный язык.*

Effective listening skills are fundamental in various aspects of life, including education, professional settings, and interpersonal relationships. In recent years, there has been a growing interest in employing innovative methodologies to enhance listening skills, particularly among diverse learner populations.

Listening is a complex receptive mental-mimic activity associated with the perception, understanding and active processing of information contained in an oral speech message. Listening is carried out as a result of performing a number of complex logical operations, such as analysis, synthesis, deduction, induction, comparison, abstraction, concretization [1].

The modern computerized world poses challenges all traditional aspects of human life. Of course, this also affected the educational sphere, in particular, teaching foreign languages. Traditional teaching methods are now becoming irrelevant and much less productive than new ones. The 21st century dictates its own rules.

The modern schoolchild is a person of the 21st millennium, a person for whom the use and application of technology is as common as simple communication with peers. This fact must be taken for granted and used in the right way when studying at school . The main goal of learning foreign languages at school is the formation of foreign language communicative skills among schoolchildren competence, that is, the ability and willingness to carry out foreign language interpersonal and intercultural communication with native speakers .

To achieve this goal, it is simply necessary to create real and imaginary communication situations in a foreign language lesson. For this purpose, a variety of teaching tools are used, among which we can highlight the use of authentic audio and video materials as the most productive and effective at the present stage. The use of media resources in lessons is important component of the education system, is an unconventional way of organizing learning through active methods of action aimed at realizing personal- oriented approach. The purpose of using audio and video materials in lessons is seen as immersing students in foreign language environment. Despite the fact that it was created artificially, it provides students with an excellent opportunity to listen and perceive authentic speech without leaving the country of the foreign language they are studying.

Auditory-pronunciation skill is the ability correctly, in accordance with the norms of the language being studied, perceive the heard sound sample and adequately reproduce. Rhythmic-intonation skill is intonation and rhythmically correct speech formatting and correct interpretation of intonation. Which method for mastering these skills is the most effective? Of course, this is imitation - repeating sounds, words, phrases after a teacher or speaker as the main teaching technique in the formation of phonetic skills. Based on this, it is very important that the same announcer has perfect sound and pronunciation skills. Therefore, it is authentic audio and video materials that act as the main engines in the formation of auditory-pronunciation and rhythmic-intonation skills of students.

The undoubted advantages of using audio and video materials in the classroom are the following:

1. The spoken language sounds lively.
2. Various ranges of voices are represented - male, women's, children's.
3. Foreign speech sounds at a fast pace (dialogues, monologues, polylogues are presented), thus achieving one of the main objectives of teaching oral speech - improving listening skills
4. Often speech is superimposed on natural interference - noise of city traffic, rain, phone call, knocking on door, works parallel to TV or radio, music plays, birdsong, the sound of water - that is, the maximum approximation of the educational video to real life is achieved.

Some advantages of video materials are: the following:

1. Watching videos has an emotional impact on students, increases the amount of long-term memory, develops their attention. In addition to the description of events video fragment, students analyze both the feelings and moods of the characters, and talk about their own impressions of watching. Thus, the educational material provided by the teacher is revealed more deeply, and emotional and evaluative vocabulary is used more widely.
2. Reflects behavior in a given situation native speakers of different ages who belong to different social environments.
3. Often, in addition to intonation, facial expressions and Gestures help to understand the speaker's attitude to the object of discussion or the relationship of the characters in the plot to each other.
4. Musical accompaniment, light and noise effects help express the director's intent for the video. Creating interference contributes to the development of the so-called “noise immunity” of perception, which is so necessary in real communication.

To the above, we can add that video films, cartoons in the foreign language being studied play very well a significant role in expanding vocabulary, helping to increase students' motivation and interest in learning a foreign language.

As audio material in foreign language lessons can be used: foreign songs, fragments foreign radio programs, audio books in a foreign language; The following can be used as video material: feature films, documentaries, cartoons,

video recordings of television news and television programs, advertising, video tours of various cities and museums around the world.

The success of listening comprehension depends on several factors, the most important of which are individual age characteristics of the listener, speed of perception, and conditions (speed, amount and size of information, supports of perception). Listening comprehension is closely

related to reading and speaking types of speech activity. Because of this, the types of speech activity have similarities and differences. These are the following: Reading, listening, and reading are receptive types of speech activity because they are aimed at receiving information. This type of speech activity is precognition and assumption [2].

Thus, the use of audio and video materials on foreign language lessons at school opens up a number of unique opportunities for both teachers and students in terms of formation of foreign language communicative competence. Audio and video materials allow you to deal with authentic speech, with an authentic manner of speaking and pronunciation, giving students a more complete understanding of the use of the target language in real life, thereby motivating them to learn a foreign language.

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